

Relationship between Self Efficacy and Job Performance and Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in Anambra State

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ABSTRACT: This study assessed the relationship between self-efficacy and job performance and satisfaction of secondary school teachers in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study. Two null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance. Correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 1,615 secondary school teachers in 32 state government owned secondary schools. Stratified random sampling technique was utilized to select a sample size of 485 teachers. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach's alpha formula which yielded reliability coefficient values of 0.88 and 0.85. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient. The results showed that there is negligible and low positive relationship between self-efficacy and job performance of secondary school teachers in Anambra State. There is moderate and substantial positive relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. The study further revealed that there is significant relationship between self-efficacy and job performance and satisfaction of secondary school teachers in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that educational agencies and professional associations should collaborate with secondary schools to organize workshops and seminars for teachers at regular interval to strengthen abilities to ensure effective performance of teachers to achieve the objectives of secondary education as entrenched in the National Policy on Education.

INTRODUCTION

Secondary school teacher is a person who is professionally trained in different higher institutions of learning who are competent in teaching secondary school subjects. Teachers are the most important members of the education system. Teachers' self-efficacy is crucial for having a successful education system thereby increasing their job performance and satisfaction. Job performance and satisfaction of teachers plays a vital role in the organization's growth (Obineli, 2013). Accordingly it is critical to focus on the self-efficacy and the job performance and satisfaction of the teachers, who are working in this sector; ultimately this decides the goal achievement of this sector. Self-efficacy is defined as individuals' beliefs that they are capable of reaching the goals and performing the specific tasks (Bandura in Robbins, Decenzo, & Coulter, 2013). Self-efficacy is one's belief about his/her capabilities. These capabilities are highly related to the perception of performance that could affect the results of events. Self-efficacy beliefs redound on the energy teachers expend whilst teaching, the goals they set, and their perceptions of self-confidence (Demir, 2018). Teachers build up self-efficacy through achieving challenging tasks. This brings about motivation which is a unique remedy to overcome the feeling of failure. Teachers' self-efficacy is not only a strong indicator of their capabilities; it also plays an important role in shaping behaviour and achievement of students. Beverborg, Slegers, Endedijk, and Van Veen (2015), identified self-efficacy as a crucial component of educational reform, effective teaching and teacher attitude. The authors further stated that teachers' satisfaction in their job contributes to the improvement of instructional practices and thus academic achievement of students. The concept of self-efficacy enables teachers to develop positive attitudes to their work environment.

Researchers suggest that self-efficacy has an effect on both students' motivation, teachers' teaching strategies and critical thinking (Demirdag, 2015). A number of research studies have proven that there is a positive influence or impact of self efficacy on performance of the employee. In addition, research shows that individuals with low levels of self-efficacy may have negative influences on both teachers' teaching methods and students' behaviors and engagement. An employee's self efficacy is associated with the performance of employee at work force (Salman, Khan, Draz, Iqbal & Aslam, 2016). It influences the work stress of employee by performing regular tasks or duties in an organization. The performance of an individual plays pivotal role in an organization. High performance of an individual brings self-efficacy, satisfaction and motivation in his career. When an employee

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reports to work, his attitude affects his work performance and can have an impact on the employee morale around him. Generally, workers with good attitudes have stronger performance, and workers with poor attitudes exhibit less-than-superior performance.

Job performance is the behaviour that can be evaluated in terms of the extent to which it contributes to organizational effectiveness (Onukwube, Iyagba & Fajana, 2010). Onukwube also opined that job performance is the behaviour and outcomes that employees engage in or bring about that are linked with and contribute to organizational goals. It is clear from these definitions that job performance is related to the extent to which an employee is able to accomplish the task assigned to him or her and how the accomplished task contributes to the realization of the organizational goal. Job performance could also be described as the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of teaching and learning processes. Owoeye (2009) asserted that variables of job performance includes effective teaching, lesson preparation, effective supervision, monitoring of students' work and disciplinary ability are virtues which teachers should uphold effectively in the school system. In this regard, secondary school teachers' job performance could be measured through annual report of their activities in terms of performance in teaching, lesson preparation, mastery of subject matter, competence, teachers' commitment to job, effective leadership, supervision, monitoring of students' work, motivation, class control and disciplinary ability of teachers.

In spite of federal government's initiatives to improve secondary education, teachers face certain challenges and issues. These issues are mainly concerned with inadequate motivation and training of teachers in the state and subsequent lack of job satisfaction and performance make them less committed to their work. Consequently they are not well motivated and do not dedicate their time to proper teaching of students nor prepare their lessons well enough to inculcate all necessary skills using adequate methods. Thus their contributions to the accomplishment of school goals are not very positive. Behaviour of an employee at work relates to his/her job performance and satisfaction. Self-efficacy have significant effects on the behaviour of a person at work. This results in poor output and consequently job performance which is apparent in several forms of misconduct on the part of the teachers. Such issues make it difficult for the teachers to cope with the academic as well as societal demands of the parents and students.

In addition, Ogbulafor, (2011) suggested that the deteriorating level of employee performance in Nigerian schools is fast becoming a serious threat to survival of secondary schools in Nigeria which needs to be addressed urgently. This might as a result of government failure in developing countries like Nigeria to improve the skills and knowledge of their civil servants through effective human resource development programmes this can boost employee performance as well as inability to exploit the capability of well experienced and trained employees (Tessema, Tesfayohannes-Beraki & Tewolde 2015). The employees are considered as the foremost business assets that expedite the regular accomplishments and tasks of an establishment (Mudah, Rafiki & Harahap, 2014). Self-efficacy strengthens employee performance, thereby encouraging creativity and productivity. A number of research studies have been discussed and proved that self-efficacy is an important factor that can affect the job performance of employees in a variety of organizations. Studies by Mojavezi and Tamis (2012); Tannady et al (2017) reported that self-efficacy affects the performance of the work of teachers. Job Performance of employees lays the foundation to achieve desired organizational goals and objectives

Self-efficacy can also help enhance job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is the behavior of employees toward organization. Job satisfaction is such a psychological attribute, whose contribution to the concept of employee performance is much more. A satisfied employee would have an emotional bond with the organization and takes pride in their membership, which paves way to keep up industrial integrity and a high morale (Shaju & Subhashini, 2017). Job satisfaction is one of the main attitudes that can influence human behavior in the work place. Job satisfaction is the degree to which individuals feel positively or negatively about their jobs. Teachers' job satisfaction therefore is the ability of the teaching job to meet teachers' needs and improve their job/teaching performance as teachers. It is important that organizations ensure job satisfaction of their employees. Teachers' self-efficacy is considered to be one of the most important factors affecting teachers' job satisfaction during their challenging teaching years. Such challenges may negatively influence teachers' motivation and job satisfaction.

Studies examining factors related to self-efficacy and job satisfaction in education have been conducted in recent years. Akomolafe and Ogunmakin (2014) found significant correlations with job satisfaction. Job satisfaction and self-efficacy was determined to be significant as well. Teachers with low levels of self-efficacy tend to be dissatisfied with their jobs, thus leaving their teaching profession. Teaching environments may include both satisfaction and stress for teachers due to demands from administrators, colleagues, students, and parents compounded by work overload, student misbehavior, and a lack of recognition for accomplishments. Research shows that dissatisfaction due to job stress may have negative effects on teacher's work and teaching effectiveness (Demirdag, 2015). Teachers, who have high levels of self-efficacy, are more open to new ideas, exhibit greater levels of planning and organization, tend to experiment new teaching strategies with their students, and have clear goals

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with higher levels of aspiration. Greater efficacy beliefs encourage teachers to have more resilience and be less critical of students, who make errors. Teachers with greater self-efficacy have greater desires for teaching and are more likely to continue staying in teaching position as they would write less numbers of discipline referrals due to having successful classroom management. However the ability of the teacher to be satisfied with job contributes to a large extent to improved performance. There appear to be no available studies in which all these performance variables are examined together in the literature. Hence, it becomes pertinent to consider certain factors that could affect job performance and satisfaction of teachers' especially secondary school teachers.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study is to determine self-efficacy as correlates of job performance and satisfaction of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study determined the:

1. Relationship between self efficacy and job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Relationship between self efficacy and job satisfaction of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between self-efficacy and job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State.

METHODS

The correlational research design was adopted in this study. Nworgu (2015) defined correlational design as the type of design that seeks to establish the relationship between two or more variables as well as indicating the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables. The study was carried out in secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was carried out in public secondary schools in Onitsha Education Zone of Anambra State which comprises of Onitsha North, Onitsha South and Ogbaru local government areas. The population for this study consisted of all the 1,615 secondary school teachers in all the 32 state government owned secondary schools in the area of the study. The sample of the study was 485, consisting of 67 teachers from Ogbaru LGA, 332 teachers from Onitsha North LGA and 86 teachers from Onitsha South LGA in Onitsha Education Zone. The proportionate stratified- random sampling technique was adopted. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire developed by the researchers. The questionnaire was structured in a four-point scale of strongly agree (SA = 4), agree (A = 3), disagree (D = 2) and strongly disagree (SD = 1).

The instrument was subjected to face validity by three experts in the field. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha method which yielded co-efficient values of .80 and .85. The researchers administered 485 copies of the instrument personally to the respondents in their schools with the aid of two research assistants who were briefed by the researchers. Out of the 485 copies of questionnaire distributed, thirty-four were incompletely filled and thirteen were not returned, hence forty-seven copies of the questionnaire were not utilized. Thus, 438 copies of the questionnaire represented 90.31% return rate were used for data analysis. The data collected for this study were analyzed using the Pearson product moment for correlation analysis to test the degree of relationship. The decision rule for the two research questions, the coefficient (r) and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the decision criteria of correlation coefficient by Best and Kahn (2003) as follows: .80 to 1.00-High to Very high, .60 to .80- Substantial, .40 to .60 - Moderate, .20 to .40 - Low and .00 to .20- Negligible (no relationship). Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze data collected. For the hypotheses, where the calculated p-value is less than the stipulated level of significance (.05), it means that there was significant difference and the hypothesis was not accepted. Conversely, where the calculated p-value is equal to or greater than the stipulated level of significance (.05), it means that there was no significant difference and the hypothesis was not rejected.

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RESULTS

Data collected with respect to the two research questions and two null hypotheses were analyzed and presented in Table 1-2

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between self-efficacy and job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 1. Correlation between self-efficacy and job performance of teachers in secondary schools

	N	Self-efficacy	Job performance	Sig	Remark
Self-efficacy	438	1	0.57		
				.02	Moderate and significant
Job performance	438	0.57	1		

Data presented in Table 1 reveals that self-efficacy of secondary school teachers has a positive relationship with their job performance ($r = 0.57$), which is herein considered moderate. This relationship also depicts that as self-efficacy increases, job performance increases by 0.57 and vice versa. The Table also depicts that the relationship between secondary school teachers self efficacy and job performance is significant ($P = .02 < .05$). Hence, the null hypothesis is not accepted. This means that there is significant relationship between self efficacy and job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 2. Correlation between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of teachers in secondary schools

	N	Self-efficacy	Job satisfaction	Sig	Remark
Self-efficacy	438	1	0.62		
				0.01	Substantial and significant
Job satisfaction	438	0.62	1		

Data presented in Table 2 indicates that self-efficacy of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State has positive relationship with their job satisfaction ($r = 0.62$), which is herein considered substantial. This relationship also depicts that as self-efficacy of secondary school teachers increases, job satisfaction increases by 0.62 and vice versa. The Table also depicts that the relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers is significant ($P = 0.01 < .05$). Hence, the null hypothesis is not accepted. This means that there is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION

Results of the study also indicated that self-efficacy of secondary school teachers has a positive relationship with their job performance and satisfaction. The relationship was statistically significant as correlation was significant at .05 level. Thus the null hypothesis was not accepted. This implies that secondary school teachers' self-efficacy was a significant predictor of job

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performance and satisfaction. The results of the study reveal that self-sufficiency is important in terms of improving job and its quality, opportunities for development and promotion, working conditions, interpersonal relationships and organizational setting. The finding is in consonance with that of Turkoglu, Cansoy and Parlar (2017) and Lai and Chen (2012) who stated that there was a significant relationship between self-efficacy and job performance and satisfaction of employees. With a high sense of self-efficacy, individuals tend to behave more positively, think more creatively which also interacts with motivation and the likely consequence of this is for such teachers to be to relatively more satisfied with their job, Self-efficacy is thus important because it assesses the role of one's self-belief as it plays into the content of behaviour which shapes job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Self-efficacy is thus important because it assesses the role of one's self-belief as it plays into the content of behaviour which shapes job performance and satisfaction. Job performance of teachers plays a vital role in the secondary schools' growth. A good teacher performance is necessary for the school, since school's success is dependent upon the teacher's creativity, innovation and commitment. The quality of teachers dictates the level of educational advancement which cannot be attained if they (teachers) are greatly dissatisfied with their jobs. Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that self-efficacy is suited for teachers' job performance and satisfaction in secondary school in Anambra State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Educational agencies and professional associations should collaborate with secondary school administrators to organize workshops and seminars for teachers at regular interval to strengthen abilities to ensure effective performance of teachers to achieve the objectives of secondary education as entrenched in the National Policy on Education.
2. Government should prioritize important motivational factors that will bring about teachers self-efficacy so as to achieve highest performance level of an employee.
3. School management should regularly devise a means in which employees demand will be met on time in order to avoid job dissatisfaction which will have a negative impact on the performance of its employees and the organization as a whole.

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